

Structural and Free Vibration Analysis of Stiffened Plate with Different Materials

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ABSTRACT

In the current era the expanding interest of fundamentally productive and essentially exemplary quality to weight proportion are for the most part served by hardened plates. These basic components are characterized as the plates fortified by Stiffeners or set of bars or ribs one or both sides of the plate. So Stiffened plates are comprised of plate components, to which for the most part load is connected, and shaft components situated at discrete dispersion's in one or both headings. The present investigation manages limited component examination of Stiffened plate by different Materials. The current investigation covering structural and modal analysis of stiffened plate with steel, Unidirectional Composite material as Single ply and laminated composite material with 5 plies. The Finite element Analysis is carried by using FEM Solver Optistruct which is inbuilt in Hypermesh. Optimization of results carried out to match the stiffness and natural frequencies with steel to substitute it.

Keyword: Mode shape, Composite, Stiffened plate, FEA. Etc.

INTRODUCTION

Steel is proven structurally good material and is most extensively used material, since it has good structural strength, low cost, more extensively available etc. but every material has cons like that steel is bit corrosion fascinate material. Steel is self-destructive material which made world to have an eye on alternative material. In the process composites are given a hope to the researchers as a substitute. Large varieties of Composite materials are available in the market and even daily updating. Stiffeners have been widely used in the composite laminated panels to overcome the reduction in the buckling load due to the presence of cutouts in the composite laminated panels. A great deal of attention has been focused on plates reinforced by stiffeners to improve their buckling behavior.

Husam Al-Qablan et al in 2010 carried Buckling of simply supported square orthotropic plates with multi-blade stiffeners is addressed herein. An approximate, semi-analytical model for such plates subjected to in-plane loading is derived results were validated using mathematica, they considered stiffened plate of 1000 mm X 1000 mm X 12 mm and compared results of steel and composite of unidirectional material and concluded that The buckling load is highly influenced by fiber orientation angles. The best performance was achieved using [45,-45, 90, 0, 0, 90,-45, 45] fiber orientations in the three loading cases. [1] Designs and response surface methodology in predicting the natural frequency of laminated composite plate under clamped boundary condition. The finite element analyses have been carried out using D-optimal design in the design of experiments technique by varying the fibre orientations, -45,0, 45 and

90. optimal solution obtained and concluded that any number of plies can be applied by varying the ply thickness [2]. To avoid the resonant behavior of the laminated structures, the results of the free vibration analysis for the laminated composite structures in the structural design are very important. Also, the composite structures whether used in civil, marine or aerospace are subjected to dynamic loads during their operation. Therefore, there exists a need for assessing the natural frequency [4].

Therefore, for assessing the natural frequency of the laminated composite plate structures, the accurate mathematical model is required. However, free vibration analysis of laminated composite plates and shells has not received ample attention. Finite element method is especially versatile and efficient for the analysis of complex structural behaviour of the composite laminated structures. In the past, the structural behavior of plates and shells using the finite element method has been studied by a variety of approaches. Ihsan Küçükrendeci and Ömer K. Morgül [5] investigated Effect of elastic boundary conditions on the linear undamped free vibrations of a five layer symmetrical laminated rectangular plate. The free vibration analysis of composite laminated right triangular plates is analyzed based on Mindlin plate theory by using the finite element method [6]. Pandit et al [7] used a nine-noded isoparametric plate-bending element for the analysis of free undamped vibration of isotropic and fiber reinforced laminated composite plates. He studied the effects of the fiber orientation, boundary conditions, material properties, and geometric ratio a/h on the vibration frequencies. Khoa and Thinh [8] developed

a rectangular non-conforming element based on Reddy's higher order shear deformation plate theory to analyze the laminated composite plates. They concluded that, the size of the mesh and the convergence of the method is involved by thickness ratio (h/a).

Patel *et al.* [9] was used the finite element method for analyzing the free vibration of laminated anisotropic composite conical cylindrical shell structures. A simple two-noded shear flexible axi-symmetric shell element based on field consistency approach is employed. Rakesh Kumar *et al.* [10] employed a C0 isoparametric finite element formulation based on a shear deformable model of higher-order theory using a higher order facet shell element to study the free vibration analysis of composite and sandwich laminates. They also studied the parametric effects of degree of orthotropy, length to-thickness ratio, plate aspect ratio, number of layers and fibre orientation on the frequency and mode shapes. Reddy *et al.* [3] used the finite element method and ANN to optimize the stacking sequence of laminated composite plates using Distance based optimal design in the design of experiments.

MATERIAL PROPERTIES

Material	Steel
Type	Isotropic
Density(ρ)	7850 kg/m ³
Poisson Ratio (ν)	0.3
Material	Glass Epoxy
Type	Orthotropic
Fiber Volume Ratio	0.65
Density(ρ)	2.1 g/cm ³
Longitudinal Young's Modulus (E_1)	60 GPa
Young's Modulus (E_2)	13 Gpa
Poisson Ratio (ν)	0.3
Longitudinal Tensile strength (σ_{xt})	1800 MPa
Longitudinal Compressive strength (σ_{xc})	650 MPa
Transverse Tensile strength (σ_{yt})	40 MPa
Transverse Compressive strength (σ_{yc})	90 MPa
Young's Modulus (E)	210 MPa

In current work stiffened plate structural and modal analysis is carried using steel, and undirectional composite of singleply and multiple plies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Finite element analysis is carried by using Optistruct solver, modelling meshing is performed in hypermesh

Figure 1 Meshed Modal of stiffened plate

Analysis-1 inputs

Modal	Stiffened plate
Dimensions	1000 mm X 1000 mm X 5 mm
Material	Steel
Boundary conditions	Fixed at four corners
Material	Steel
Type	Isotropic
Density(ρ)	7850 kg/m ³
Poisson Ratio (ν)	0.3
Young's Modulus (E)	210 MPa
Type of Element	Hexa or Brick
Elemental Property	Pshell
Load	Uniform pressure

Structural analysis Output of steel stiffened plate:

Figure 2 Stress Distribution in Steel Stiffened Plate

Figure 3 Deformation in Steel Stiffened Plate

It has shown that maximum Deformation of plate will occur at centre and maximum stress will occur at the supports, maximum deformation will be around 70mm and maximum stress will be around 85 MPa.

Mode Shapes of Steel Stiffened plate:

Following are the first 5 Mode shapes are obtained in modal analysis of Steel Stiffened plate

Figure 4 Mode Shape-I

Figure 5 Mode Shape-II

Figure 7 Mode Shape-IV

Figure 6 Mode Shape-III

Figure 8 Mode Shape-V

Analysis-2 inputs

Modal	Stiffened plate
Dimensions	1000 mm X 1000 mm X 5 mm
Boundary conditions	Fixed at four corners
Material	Glass Epoxy laminated composite
Type	Orthotropic
Fiber Volume Ratio	0.65
Density(ρ)	2.1 g/cm ³
Longitudinal Young's Modulus (E_1)	60 GPa
Young's Modulus (E_2)	13 Gpa
Poisson Ratio (ν)	0.3
Longitudinal Tensile strength (σ_{xt})	1800 MPa
Longitudinal Compressive strength (σ_{xc})	650 MPa
Transverse Tensile strength (σ_{yt})	40 MPa
Transverse Compressive strength (σ_{yc})	90 MPa
Type of Element	Hexa or Brick
Elemental Property	Pcompp
Load	Uniform pressure
No.of Plies	5 Layers

Closed view of Meshed Modal

Model Info: C:/Users/harshavardhan/Documents/HM/LAYERED COMPOSITE/laminated composite stiffened plate modal.hm*

Figure 9 Closed view of Meshed Modal of laminated composite stiffened plate

In current work composite considered with 5 plies of uniform thickness and ply orientations and properties are shown in following table, glass fibers with epoxy matrix are considered for composite material.

Composite Plies Details:

Ply Name	Ply ID	Card image	Mat Name	Thickness	Orientation	Output Results	TMANU	DRAPE_ID	ESID
ply1	1	PLY	glass epoxy	1	0	Yes		0	1
ply2	2	PLY	glass epoxy	1	45	Yes		0	2
ply3	3	PLY	glass epoxy	1	90	Yes		0	3
ply4	4	PLY	glass epoxy	1	-45	Yes		0	4
ply5	5	PLY	glass epoxy	1	0	Yes		0	5

Structural analysis Output of Laminated Composite stiffened plate:

Figure 10 Deformation of Composite Stiffened plate

When we compare the deformation and Vonmises stress in Steel and composite, composite showed that bit weaker than steel, but in the view of corrosion and manufacturing feasibility we can adopt the composite in place of steel

Laminated Composite Stiffened Plate Modal Analysis Result

Figure 14 Mode Shape-III

Figure 15 Mode Shape –IV

Figure 16 Mode Shape –V

Figure 12 Mode Shape-I

Figure 13 Mode Shape –II

In the below graph it is clear that natural frequency of composite is almost half of steel, since steel is possessing more stiffness it will have more natural frequencies and we can say by using polymer composite reaching 50% of Steel and we can replace them.

Figure 14 Comparison of Natural Frequencies of Steel and Composite Stiffened Plate

CONCLUSION

Stiffened Plate is Modeled and Performed structural and modal analysis in Hypermesh by varying the material of the plate with fixed supports. The Following Conclusions were obtained

- ❖ Structural analysis is carried on the steel and composite plate it is clear that steel plate has less deformation and more stress inclusion in the plate for the applied pressure. Even though composite plate has more deformation since it has less stress inclusion it can be replaced.
- ❖ From Modal analysis natural frequency of composite is almost 50% of steel, since steel is possessing more stiffness it will have more natural frequencies and we can say by using polymer composite reaching 50% of Steel and we can replace them
- ❖ In both aspects from the simulated data it is suggested to replace the steel stiffened plate with 5 plies laminated Composite.

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